

Science Europe Reaction to Mariya Gabriel's Public Hearing at the European Parliament

Research is Essential to All EU Policy Areas

Brussels, 2 October 2019

Science Europe warmly welcomes the strong commitment from Mariya Gabriel, Commissioner-designate for Innovation and Youth, to support excellent research in Europe. As she emphasised during her public hearing at the European Parliament on 30 September, research is essential for Europe to address the societal challenges, and lead the transition to a sustainable and digital economy and society.

High-quality research is key for the EU's competitiveness, sustainable growth, and its ability to develop disruptive technologies and breakthrough innovation. To meet the Sustainable Development Goals the EU needs to increase its capacity to produce world-leading research. It is therefore very welcome that Mariya Gabriel expressed her support to the European Parliament's position to increase the budget for Horizon Europe to €120 billion under the next Multiannual Financial Framework.

The development of synergies between research, innovation, and education policies are necessary to ensure that European research delivers for people and society. "We are delighted that Mariya Gabriel will work closely with the other Commissioners to ensure that research contributes to EU objectives. Collaboration will be a key factor in the success of her ambitious mandate," said Lidia Borrell-Damián, Secretary General of Science Europe.

Mariya Gabriel also restated her intention to include stakeholders and researchers in policy-making through an open and collaborative approach. "A partnership approach, where stakeholders, researchers, and research organisations provide strong input is essential to strengthening the European Research Area and to implement evidence-based policies," added Lidia Borrell-Damián. Science Europe therefore strongly supports the Commissioner-designate's ambition to propose a forward-looking vision for the European Research Area, and looks forward to collaborating with Mariya Gabriel and her team.